

COMMUNICATIVE PROBLEMS IN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *The article discusses ways to accelerate the process of mastering a foreign language, the need to move from the classical to the communicative approach in teaching a foreign language. The main activities and requirements for a foreign language accountant when using a communicative approach are presented.*

Key words: *Communicative methods, encryption, decryption, parallelism, cult urological.*

At present, the need to learn English in various spheres of human activity has become generally accepted. English is thought throughout all the years of study, in all specialties and the main task of training is the mastery of students' communication skills in English. If we consider various specialties, then much attention is paid to teaching students to "communication" in different spheres. The emphasis is put on the communicative methods of instruction. However, here we are faced with a number of communicative problems of linguistics.

It is a well-known fact that an indispensable condition for the implementation of any communicative act must be a mutual knowledge of realities by the speaker and the hearer, which is the basis of language communication. These values have received in linguistics the name of background knowledge. A word reflecting an object or phenomenon of the reality of a particular society not only mean it but also creates some backgrounds associated with this word.

The experience of teaching shows that even at advanced stages of training, students admit a significant number constructions in conversational practice.

Incorrect use of these structures in the composition of a complex sentence leads to a violation of the logic of the utterance and, as a consequence, to non- fulfillment of the tasks of communication. In this regards, we see the need for more detailed equipping of this topic and the development of relevant recommendations.

Another obstacle on the way to solving the communicative problem of linguistics is the correct perception of the said form, that is the perception of what of what has been said.

The next problem is the translation of the form into a common meaning. At this stage, it is important that the listener knows at least one, the most common meaning of the word, which was uttered. Therefore, when teaching English as a means of communication, it is important to make it clear to students that a person perceives what is said through their individual and cultural prism, and therefore, it is necessary, as accurately as possible, to convey all the meanings that the word carries in it. [1. P;541-545]

The transition from cultural to individual values is manifested in the projection of cultural values through the prism of some of their own properties, attitudes. This is the barrier in communication, which is called psychological, and is the most difficult to overcome in communication between individuals, because for all people the mechanism of "encryption" and "decryption" is different and depends on various reasons, one of which is the different psychology of people.

Therefore, the urgency of the communicative problems has now acquired an unprecedented poignancy. This problem is also connected with one of the problems of the theory of translation, namely with the methods of transfer of the equivalent vocabulary. Vocabulary, which has no analogues in a different culture. It, in turn, creates a great obstacle in communication between people of different cultures. The solution to this problem we see in the expansion of background knowledge of students.

Background vocabulary are words or expressions that have additional content and accompanying semantic or stylistic nuances that overlap with its basic meaning, known to the speaker and listener belonging to a given language culture. Therefore, an important stage in teaching communication is to familiarize students with the realities, traditions and customs of English-speaking countries.

In this course of teaching a foreign language much attention is paid to the elements of linguistics. If earlier regional information accompanied the basic course of a foreign language only as a comment when studying a particular materials, nowadays the linguistic and cultural aspects is an integral part of the lessons of a foreign language, as it increasingly becomes necessary to teach what lies "behind the language", that is, culture of the country of the studies language.

The use of the linguistic and cultural aspects contributes to the formation of the motivation of the teaching. When learning a language, simultaneously with the condition of each lexeme, the lexical concept associated with it is formed. If the lexeme is acquired and articulated correctly, this does not yet indicate that the lexical concept has been completed. In the educational process, it should be borne in mind that the word is simultaneously a sign of reality and a unit of language. Therefore, nonequivalent and background vocabulary needs comment, requires special attention of the teacher. Equivalent vocabulary is the property of culture. If we compare two national cultures, then we can conclude that they never completely coincide. This follows from the fact that each language consists of national and international elements, and for each culture, the totality of these elements will be different.

Since there is parallelism between language and culture, it is necessary to talk about national and international elements not only in cultures, but also in the languages of their servants.

The acquisition of students in the culture of English-speaking countries is an integral part in teaching a foreign language. In our practice, we constantly draw the attention of students to the cultural aspects, namely, what traditions and customs exist in the culture of the country whose language the study. We introduce students to language and among its existence.

In addition, the content of the national culture also includes the social component, on the basis of which knowledge about the realities and right of the countries of the

communication directly with the native speaker of the language being studied, the teacher needs to explain certain features of the culture of native speakers, we often face the problem of students' lack of understanding of the characteristics and culture of the native speakers. In this regards, we are trying to select the language material reflecting the culture of the country of the studied language, the so-called realities. In realities, the closeness between language and culture is most clearly manifested.[2.p;23-23, 84-85]

A distinctive feature of reality from other words of the language is the nature of its subject content, the close connection of the designated reality of the object or phenomenon with the national, on the one hand, and the historical interval of time – on the hand. Reality as a linguistic phenomenon is most closely connected with the culture of the country of the studied language, since it has a national and historical color.

Following the communicative system- activity approach in the study of the English language, we in our practice try to implement such a method of instruction, in which the systematically, systematized and interconnected learning is conducted as a means of communication in the context of the verbal activity modeled in the classroom, in integral and integral part of the overall (extra linguistic) activity. Communicative system- activity approach implies a complete and optimal systematization of the relationship between the components of the content of training.

These include the system of general (for example, extra-linguistic, pedagogical activity, the system of speech activity, the system of speech communication, communication, interaction and mutual perception), the system of the foreign language being studied, the system correlation of native and foreign languages their consciously comparative analysis, the system speech mechanisms speech generation, speech perception, speech interaction.

As a result of this approach, the system of knowledge of a foreign language is formed, implemented and operates as a means of communication in the broadest sense of the word.

So, the materials used in teaching should form the language competence the possession of the language material for its use in the form of speech utterance, sociolinguistic competence the ability to use language units in accordance with communication situations.

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